

STUDIES ON LIPASE FROM OIL SEEDS. PART XIII. HYDROLYSIS OF SOME ESTERS BY RICINUS LIPASE FROM CASTOR SEED

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Hydrolysis of some aliphatic esters by ricinus lipase from castor seed has been carried out in order to study the effect of the nature of the alcoholic group on the enzymic hydrolysis of esters.

Ramakrishnan and Nevgi (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 33) studied in detail the enzymic hydrolysis of different propionates and butyrates of a homologous series and found that the maximum percentage hydrolysis decreased from methyl to amyl ester.

The hydrolysis of the following esters was carried out using acetone-dried lipase in order to study the effect of the nature of the alcoholic group (the structure of the alcohol) on the hydrolysis of esters by lipase: normal, secondary and tertiary butyl and amyl esters of propionic and butyric acids.

EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals used were:

1. <i>n</i> -Amyl propionate: Mol. wt.	144.21	<i>d</i> , 0.876 g./c.c.	b.p. 164°
2. <i>sec.</i> " "	—	—	—
3. <i>tert.</i> " "	—	0.876	142°
4. <i>n</i> -Amyl butyrate	158.24	0.871	185°
5. <i>sec.</i> " "	"	0.862	173°
6. <i>tert.</i> " "	"	0.865	164°
7. <i>n</i> -Butyl propionate	130.8	0.888	145°
8. <i>sec.</i> " "	—	0.866	132°
9. <i>tert.</i> " "	—	0.873	147°
10. <i>n</i> -Butyl butyrate	144.21	0.872	166°
11. <i>sec.</i> " "	—	—	—
12. <i>tert.</i> " "	—	0.872	165°

Each set of the experiments consisted of 0.018 g. mol. of ester solution, 1 g. of acetone-dried lipase, 10 c.c. of ether solvent and a few drops of toluene kept in a corked bottle. Initially 1 c.c. of it was taken and 25 c.c. neutral alcohol added, warmed and titrated against *N*/10-NaOH. This gave the blank reading. After keeping the mixture in the incubator at 37° at different intervals of time, 1 c.c. portion of it was taken, 25 c.c. neutral alcohol added, warmed and titrated against *N*/10-NaOH. From the difference in readings for the sample and the blank, the percentage hydrolysis was calculated. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I
Hydrolysis of esters by *ricinus lipase*.

Esters.	Percentage hydrolysis on the					
	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	4th day.	5th day.	6th day.
<i>n</i> -Butyl propionate	20.4	24.7	31.2	34.5	33.6	—
<i>sec.</i> " "	18.9	23.5	30.9	34.0	33.2	—
<i>tert.</i> " "	18.2	22.8	29.7	33.7	31.8	—
<i>n</i> -Butyl butyrate	21.2	23.8	30.9	33.7	32.3	—
<i>sec.</i> " "	20.5	22.9	29.7	33.1	31.9	—
<i>tert.</i> " "	19.8	21.7	29.5	32.8	32.3	—
<i>n</i> -Amyl propionate	14.9	25.8	33.7	32.5	—	—
<i>sec.</i> " "	13.8	24.7	30.8	31.5	31.2	—
<i>tert.</i> " "	12.9	23.6	28.9	31.0	30.7	—
<i>n</i> -Amyl butyrate	19.8	28.1	29.2	31.2	30.5	—
<i>sec.</i> " "	18.5	26.2	28.5	30.5	29.7	—
<i>tert.</i> " "	17.8	24.9	27.6	29.8	28.1	—

From Table I, it is found that in case of butyl as well as amyl esters of propionic and butyric acids, the percentage hydrolysis decreases in the order: normal, secondary and tertiary ester. There is a marked difference among the primary, secondary and tertiary esters, in which the structure of the alcohols is different, which will help us to differentiate among primary, secondary and tertiary esters. It can also be seen that in each case, the percentage hydrolysis depends only on the nature of the alcohol and not on the number of carbon atoms in the acid as the percentage hydrolysis only changes with the nature of the alcohol and remains almost the same with the change in the number of carbon atoms in the acid.

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